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REVIEW: FOODS SUPPLEMENTS FOR WEIGHT GAIN AND WEIGHT LOSS IN HUMAN

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Abstract: *Making sensible dietary decisions is essential to living a healthy life. Choosing meals that increase good cholesterol over bad cholesterol will help you remain healthy overall and avoid gaining weight. The impact of different dietary groups on weight and health is studied in this abstract. It explores topics such as how meat products are digested, the advantages of soaking groundnuts, the effects of pepper on digestion, the use of natural sweeteners, the many kinds of fish, the significance of selecting the correct oils, and the nutritional worth of eggs, coconuts, and bananas.*

Keywords: *Weight gain, balance diet, Body Mass Index*

INTRODUCTION

Making the appropriate eating choices is all that's required to lead a healthy life. You can avoid gaining weight if you selected foods that raise good cholesterol instead of those that raise bad cholesterol; the difference is evident. Let's now examine the healthful foods that are high in healthy fats [1]. Weight loss and gain are linked to variations in energy expenditure in the body's metabolically active component.

These changes are non-adaptive and passive. However, weight change does not quite match the estimate based on energy imbalance calculations. The majority of these changes are not adaptive and occur passively. However, weight

change does not quite match the estimate based on energy imbalance calculations.

This study focuses on the nutritional supplements which are providing positive and negative results to the human. Therefore a clear analysis of the nutritional content of food is required to take decision whether that food is good for health or not. This will provide a clear idea for people to make their diet.

OBJECTIVES

To identify the nutritional supplements which can provide body weight gain or body weight reduction to take decision on the diet.

1. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1.1. Healthy fat-containing foods to help reduce weight

MEAT PRODUCTS

In general, foods that are carnivorous take 12 hours to fully digest. Once they do, it takes three days for their waste to be eliminated. In actuality, the stool is the same as it was three days before, even for individuals who consume meat on a daily basis. And on a diet high in meat, 1/3 share is just power. Deduction is also included in 2/3 Stock [2]. Consequently, it is best to stay away from meat because the energy it contains is insufficient to eliminate its waste. Meat protein also includes certain necessary amino acids. Plant-based diets do not include them. Meat is therefore necessary. If meat is necessary, it should be consumed with pepper in smaller amounts. Meat fats benefit from poultry flesh [3]. That is, meat can raise bad cholesterol in mammals that consume both meat and fat (goat, beef, and pork). In a similar vein, we tend to get fat by eating broiler chickens, which are produced with a lot of pesticides and hormones [4,5]. The purpose of these estrogen hormones is to feminize and develop guys quickly. Women are becoming more obese and experiencing menstrual issues. Overfeeding broiler chicks throws off their hormonal balance and makes them more susceptible to depression. Or you might have some country chicken. Put differently, meat from animals that eat both meat and fat (such as pigs, cows, and goats) may increase unhealthy cholesterol. Similarly, consuming broiler chickens, which are raised with a lot of hormones and chemicals, causes us to gain weight. Menstrual problems and obesity are on the rise among women. Broiler chicks that are overfed experience hormonal imbalances and are more prone to depression. Maybe some country chicken would be better [6].

SIX HOURS OF SOAKING GROUNDNUTS IN WATER

The groundnuts get more refined and revitalized after soaking in water for six hours. When consumed uncooked, it provides vital nutrients (vitamins), enzymes (enzymes), and protein (protein) that aid in the breakdown of fat. There's no denying that heating or roasting peanuts adds unhealthy fat [4].

PEPPER

Any non-vegetarian dish that has a small amount of pepper powder added to it will digest fat more quickly. Nutrients (minerals) also help in the digestion of fat. Pepper contains phytonutrients called phytofactors, which help reduce the toxicity of non-vegetarian meals. Food that isn't vegetarian and contains a lot of spices, such as green chilies, might be challenging to digest [6].

NATURAL SWEETENERS

Natural sweeteners, including honey, black juice, natural jaggery, dried grapes, dates, and sweetened fruit juices, all aid in the effective breakdown of fat. It is loaded with B vitamins and carbohydrates, both of which provide rapid energy and aid in the breakdown of lipids. As evidenced, the digestive aid jaggery combined with coconut sweets provides [7].

FISHES

Pond fish are inferior to sea fish. Small fish with delicate skin are the ideal marine fish. High-density metals, such as mercury (sometimes referred to as heavy metals), should be avoided since they can deposit on the skin. Fish oil is a brain fuel that is readily absorbed [8].

OILS

Food that is not vegetarian is not as harmful as oil. When non-vegetarian food is fried in oil, it turns into extremely unhealthy fat. Similar to this, spent oil turns into highly saturated fat when it is reheated and used again [1]. Olive oil is the best type of oil. Not even two or three bakings will cause it to become bad fat. Omega-9 trans fats in olive oil can improve skin health and immunity. Compared to other oils, this one is three times denser. Although it has a hefty cost, your heart is worth more. Coconut oil is the second-greatest oil, right after olive oil. After being cooked a few times, this also doesn't spoil [9]. Goodwill is the third-best number. Both coconut oil and olive oil can eliminate kapha and pitta. Phlegm

and body heat can be eliminated using neem oil. Ghee gets its name from the fact that it is a healthy cooking oil. All other oils, excluding these three, are beneficial to health. Dupu is the oil used for all other recommended heart-healthy oils. Indeed, sunflowers are sent to temperate locations, as is proper for all groundnut and soy oils. Ghee is the best oil for hot nations like ours [7].

EGG

Almonds and pistachios: These foods are rich in omega-3 fatty acids. There is a certain kind of fat. It has the ability to reduce cholesterol [8,9]. Because they might be difficult to digest, these pulses should only be consumed rarely. When consumed with honey, they are easily digested [10,12].

COCONUT

The all-purpose component is coconut. It is a fantastic diet that is heavy in fat and has all of the required amino acids. These nutrients are necessary for proper digestion. Coconut has both positive and negative effects on food when used in cooking [11,12]. If coconut is lightly fried instead of boiling, it will be easier to digest; otherwise, it can be somewhat difficult. It is recommended that people with diabetes and high cholesterol avoid coconut. They make this suggestion since they are unsure of how to improve their digestion [10]. They now consume predominantly tomato or onion chutney as a result of their advice. Onion grinding harms neurons. Kidney stones may develop as a result of grinding tomatoes. They shift from being good to being bad. Coconut is easily absorbed when consumed with natural jaggery or pepper. If someone believes that coconuts are unhealthy, they should at least consider Malayalees [9].

BANANA

The avocado, or Albagata fruit, has a lot of omega-3 fatty acids. The type has a low-fat content. This fruit provides energy when sick and is easily digested [12]. Consume foods that promote healthy cholesterol, a light blood vessel, and prevent obesity. Obtain resilient skin, reduce nerves, and lead a healthy existence [7].

WEIGHT GAIN FOODS

In this world, waste is added, body fat increases, and no one is committed to living a particular way. However, we drown because we don't know how [16]. All we have to do is keep from being bloated, and success will come. We won't acquire fat if we recognize and steer clear of the meals that contribute to our

weight gain [4,11]. We shall examine foods that raise bad cholesterol next in this chapter.

FOODS HIGH IN FAT THAT CONTRIBUTE TO BODY FAT:

STARCHY FOOD

All of the leftover flour will change into fat after providing us with the energy we need to work when our labor consumes more starch than we require. Artificial sweeteners found in Alva, succharin, artificially flavored cold beverages, maida (parotta) foods made with white sugar and incomplete starches, White Night, White Semiya, and noodles can all be converted into unhealthy fats [7,13]. These consist of nutrients (vitamins) and minerals (minerals). When they are taken out, they first convert to harmful glucose and, subsequently, to fat [7].

FAST FOODS

Quick food (quick food) More harmful cholesterol than any other food can be found in them. Fast food that is heated too quickly loses all of its nutrition [10]. We enjoy consuming these nutritionally and flavor-deficient items, to which fake chemical flavourings like Ajinomoto and soda are added to boost our spirits. In actuality, once they have cooled down, these meals cannot be consumed. The nutritional value of it will then be known. When food is cooked to perfection, nutrients are absorbed into the food without spoiling, and the food's viscosity (colloidal characteristic) is retained without deterioration [7,9].

GREEN CHILIES

Consuming too many green chilies can cause acid reflux, harm to the liver, and difficulties digesting fat and protein. The result is an increase in the synthesis of harmful cholesterol [7]. The brain is unable to distinguish where the harmful fat is stored; thus, another blast of green chilies will melt our nerves [8,12].

POTATOES

Potatoes are a starchy meal that spreads like wildfire in colder climates. In some locations, people only eat it as a starchy food. It will be the ideal diet for them because it provides some warmth in that chilly atmosphere [10,12]. That's all. For those of us who reside in tropical nations, taking this will cause our bodies to overheat and harm our livers. It also aids in the breakdown of fat. Moreover, we eat far too much starch from potatoes and grains like rice and wheat. Therefore,

too much starch for our work results in too much fat, which causes obesity. Potatoes often make people feel bloated in hot climates [4,12]. Cooking and peeling potatoes result in flatulence. Fried food produces flatulence [13].

SOUR FLAVOURED FOODS

Acidic diets impair bile and overstimulate the liver, which interferes with the breakdown of fat. It is preferable to consume less acidic food, particularly when consuming non-vegetarian cuisine. It is best to avoid taking mango in particular. Astringents and spices, particularly pepper, can aid in the vegetable's simpler digestion [4,12].

CRUMBS

Crunchy and acidic, they deplete stomach moisture and impair splenic digestion. As a result, when the liver has less access to splenic digestive capacity, fat digestion is impacted. Ultimately, all the fat in junk food is converted to unhealthy fat [7,12].

TRANS-FAT CONTAINING FOODS (TRANS FAT)

An artificially altered fatty food is vanaspati (dalta). Other fatty foods include ice cream, processed foods, and paneer. Processed milk with skimmed milk raises harmful cholesterol levels and harms the liver and stomach [2,7].

CHILLED AND COOL FOODS

Milkshakes, ice cream, and cold water (ice water). Cold meals and beverages impair the spleen's ability to digest food, and as a result of the liver's decreased energy supply, undesirable fat is produced [3,5].

OIL FRIED FOODS

Begin to prepare a salad for dinner. If you consume it, it will be correctly digested. The same will be broken down, but some nutrients will be lost if it is gently cooked. Food that is overcooked loses all of its nutrition [7]. The nutrients in the same food will be eliminated, and all of the fat will transform into bad fat if it is cooked in oil and then consumed. Consequently, it is preferable to fry meals less rather than add excessive amounts of oil [9,18].

YOGHURT AND CURD

Avoiding curd won't make you gain weight if that's your goal. Break down the curd (18 hours pass). Yogurt can therefore only be consumed throughout the day. Yogurt consumed at night enters the colon before being broken down; this causes retention, which manifests as constipation. Undigested yogurt ferments, foams up, gets greasy, and adds to body fat along with bad fat [9,14].

PICKLES

Pickles, being strong in sour and salt, produce too many enzymes, which cause them to empty before digestion is finished [15]. Consuming a lot of food when consuming pickles causes surplus food to be converted to fat [4,9].

DRINKING WATER

Drinking too much water when you're not thirsty dilutes digestive enzymes, hinders digestion, and raises harmful cholesterol levels. Avoiding drinking water while eating is preferable. It is also preferable to wait 30 minutes after eating before drinking any water. Drink only water when you're thirsty. Eating when you're hungry does not cause weight gain [6,12].

CHOCOLATE AND BISCUITS

Both foods cause waste retention and impede the liver's and kidneys' ability to digest food. salty flatulence that is also biscuit-like. Chocolate dries the body, fractures the blood, and taints the bile. Bad fat accumulates as a result of this. Steer clear of body fat and go for healthy fat foods instead of unhealthy ones. a thin blood vessel, obtain resilient skin, calm nerves, and lead a healthy existence [1,6].

CHICKPEAS

Skin-less chickpeas are also really delicious. When eaten as dal, it gets even worse [17]. Mouthwash can interfere with the liver's ability to metabolize fat. You can have non-flatulent chickpeas as a snack in place of chickpeas [19-21].

CONCLUSION

The data emphasizes how important food decisions are to maintaining a healthy lifestyle and managing weight. Choosing foods high in healthy fats, such as fish, eggs, coconut, bananas, groundnuts, pepper, natural sweeteners, and some meats, helps people lose weight and feel better overall. On the other hand, since starchy foods, fast food, green chilies, potatoes, sour foods, trans fats, and other foods can

cause weight gain and other negative health impacts, caution is advised against consuming large amounts of these items. The conclusion highlights the critical connection between food choices and a healthy lifestyle by highlighting moderation and educated consumption.

REFERENCE

- [1] Wu, T., Liu, R., Zhang, L., Rifky, M., Sui, W., Zhu, Q., ... & Zhang, M. (2022). Dietary Intervention on Depression-A review. *Food & Function*. 13, 12475-12486
- [2] Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A. The impact of myoglobin levels on the color of chicken sausage, The scientific and practical conference of the republic (2023) 424-427.
- [3] Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A. The impact of water holding capacity and CaCl₂ addition levels on processed meat quality, Current Problems of Creating and Using High Technologies for processing mineral Resources in Uzbekistan (2023) 66-67.
- [4] Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A. The impact of sodium ascorbate in processed meat, Current problems of creating and using high technologies for processing mineral resources in uzbekistan (2023) 54-55.
- [5] Kumara, K., Rifky, M., & Samadiy, M. (2023). Application and regulation of nitrate and nitrite in manufacturing of chicken sausage. Theoretical and experimental chemistry and modern problems of chemical technology, 1(01).
- [6] Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Dissanayake, K., Ermat, S., & Samadiy, M. (2024). Development and evaluation of an automated irrigation system for ordinary agriculture farm. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 480, p. 03013). EDP Sciences.
- [7] Rifky, M., Serkaev, K., & Samadiy, M. (2023). Technology Development to Incorporate Functional Oil Sources in Yoghurt to Improve Functional Properties. *Journal of Coastal Life Medicine*, 11, 928-938.
- [8] Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A., The diverse function of sodium chloride in meat products in meat processing., Current problems of creating and using high technologies for processing mineral resources in uzbekistan (2023)
- [9] Dissanayake, K., Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Makhmayorov, J., Rakhimkulov, S., & Abdullayev, B. (2023, November). Technology Development to Measure Chemical and Oxidative Stability of Edible Oils Using Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1275, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.
- [10] Aouichat, S., Chayah, M., Bouguerra-Aouichat, S., & Agil, A. (2020). Time-restricted feeding improves body weight gain, lipid profiles, and atherogenic indices in cafeteria-diet-fed rats: role of browning of inguinal white adipose tissue. *Nutrients*, 12(8), 2185.

- [11] Ataxodjayeva, I. D., Akramova, R. R., Rifky, M., & Dissanayake, K. (2023). Study of mineral substances in easily digestible rabbit meat. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 90-93).
- [12] Sun, Y., Liu, B., Snetselaar, L. G., Wallace, R. B., Shadyab, A. H., Chen, G. C., ... & Bao, W. (2023). Chocolate Consumption in Relation to All-Cause and Cause-Specific Mortality in Women: The Women's Health Initiative. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 123(6), 902-911.
- [13] Liu, R., Ci, X., Liu, L., Wang, X., Rifky, M., Liu, R.,... & Zhang, M. (2024). Chitosan entrapping of sodium alginate/Lycium barbarum polysaccharide gels for the encapsulation, protection and delivery of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* with enhanced viability. *Inter. Jour. of Biolo. Macromo.*, 129615.
- [14] Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Dissanayake, K., Orif, U., & Samadiy, M. (2024). Production of yoghurts with the addition of microencapsulated cinnamon, garlic and cumin oil with corn oil. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 480, p. 03014). EDP Sciences.
- [15] Dissanayake, K., Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Makhmayorov, J., Rakhimkulov, S., Abdullayev, B., & Samadiy, M. (2023, November). Development of Technology to Incorporate Curry leaves (*Murraya Koenjii*) to Develop Functional Chicken Sausage and Evaluation of Chemical Properties. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1275, No. 1, p. 012008). IOP Publishing.
- [16] Tieri, M., Ghelfi, F., Vitale, M., Vetrani, C., Marventano, S., Lafranconi, A., ... & Grosso, G. (2020). Whole grain consumption and human health: an umbrella review of observational studies. *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition*, 71(6), 668-677.
- [17] Dunn, C. G., Gao, K. J., Soto, M. J., & Bleich, S. N. (2021). Disparities in adult fast-food consumption in the US by race and ethnicity, national health and nutrition examination survey 2017–2018. *American journal of preventive medicine*, 61(4), e197-e201.
- [18] World Health Organization. (2020). The state of food security and nutrition in the world 2020: transforming food systems for affordable healthy diets (Vol. 2020). Food & Agriculture Organization.
- [19] Zhao, Y., Liu, R., Qi, C., Li, W., Rifky, M., Zhang, M., ... & Sui, W. (2021). Mixing oil-based microencapsulation of garlic essential oil: impact of incorporating three commercial vegetable oils on the stability of emulsions. *Foods*, 10(7), 1637.
- [20] Dini, I., & Mancusi, A. (2023). Weight Loss Supplements. *Molecules*, 28(14), 5357.